

THE PROSPECT TO TAKE EDUCATION LAW TO A NEW LEVEL

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Abstract: In this thesis, quotes are given about the new law on education, types of education, reforms in the education system. The goals and objectives of the research conducted in connection with the study of reforms in the educational system are determined.

Key words: the law on education, the main difference, the essence of the law on education, family education, independent education, external education, part-time, evening, distance education, dual education.

Introduction.

The new version of the Law "On Education" was published. The law was published in the newspaper "Khalk Sozi" and entered into force on September 24, 2020.¹

The main differences of the new law.

In the new edition of the Law on Education, some elements differ from the previous application with a number of changes. In particular, the new law is aimed at creating new opportunities, broadening the scope of education and education for the entire population.

First, the classification of forms of education has been expanded:

- separated from production (daytime) and without separation (external, evening, remote);
- theoretical - on the basis of the educational organization, practical - dual education conducted together at the student's workplace;
- family education and independent education;
- education and training of adults;
- inclusive education for children (individuals) with physical, mental, sensory or mental disabilities;
- Externship education - includes independent mastering of educational programs, and according to its results, students pass final and state certifications

¹ O'zbekiston Respublikasining Qonuni, 23.09.2020 yildagi O'RQ-637-son <https://lex.uz/docs/-9013007>

in state educational institutions;

➤ personnel training in the field of defense, security and law enforcement activities.

Secondly, the powers of the Cabinet of Ministers, the State Inspectorate for Quality Control of Education (Educational Inspectorate), the President, the agency for the development of creativity and specialized schools, as well as the ministries and local government bodies were clarified.

Thirdly, more attention is paid to the legal status of all participants of the educational process:

➤ educational organizations - their establishment, reorganization and liquidation, charter requirements;

➤ pedagogical staff, students, their parents and other legal representatives - on rights, obligations and guarantees. Measures for social protection of the participants of the educational process are defined.

Fourthly, issues related to the introduction of state educational standards and requirements, curricula and programs into the educational process, and experimental and innovative activity education into the field of education have been regulated. The mechanism of admission, including targeted admission, is described;

Fifth, regulatory and control levers are regulated by the state, the former include:

➤ licensing of the activities of non-governmental educational organizations - licenses are issued by the Educational Inspection for an unlimited period, separately for each type of education;

➤ certification and state accreditation of educational organizations - carried out by the Education Inspection for a period of 5 years. In this case, non-governmental educational organizations are considered to have been accredited for 5 years from the date of obtaining the license. Organizations that have passed state accreditation are included in a special register, information about which is posted on the website of the Education Inspectorate;

➤ recognition of a document on education received in a foreign country after January 1, 1992, as well as apostille on official documents in the field of education. Recognition and apostille are also within the jurisdiction of the Education Inspectorate;

The educational inspectorate has the right to:

➤ implementation of quality control and monitoring of the educational process in non-state educational organizations - by notifying the business

ombudsman;

➤ in cases where the content and quality of education provided by educational organizations are found to be inconsistent with the legal documents on education - to make submissions to them regarding their elimination. In case of non-fulfilment of the application - cancellation of the state accreditation certificate of the educational organization.²

The President signed the Law "On Education". With this law, the laws "On Education" and "On the National Program of Personnel Training" adopted in 1997 have lost their force.³

The President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed the Law "On Education" on September 23, the press service of the Ministry of Justice reported. This document was accepted by the deputies of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis in the second reading on May 19 and approved by the Senate on August 7.

According to the law, the types of education are as follows:

- preschool education and upbringing;
- general secondary and secondary special education;
- professional education;
- higher education;
- post-secondary education;
- personnel retraining and improving their qualifications;
- extracurricular education.

It is known that the Law "On Education" was adopted in 1997 and does not meet today's requirements for ensuring the quality of education.

Adoption of this new law will ensure that the issue of education is inextricably linked with education. With this, it is intended to bring each young person to the enlightened maturity as a person at the current stage of our social life.

In addition, special attention is paid to the issue of preschool education and upbringing, which serves to improve the type of continuous education aimed at teaching and educating preschool children, preparing children for general secondary education.

At the same time, starting from the pre-school education system, general secondary and secondary special, vocational education, higher education, retraining of personnel and improving their qualifications, the integrity of

² O'zbekiston Respublikasining Qonuni, 23.09.2020 yildagi O'RQ-637-son <https://lex.uz/docs/-5013007>

³ O'zbekiston Respublikasining Qonuni, 29.08.1997 yildagi 464-I-son <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-16188?ONDATE=05.01.2018%2002>

extracurricular education, content-wise sequence Special attention is paid to ensuring continuity.

In addition, it is decided to carry out education on the basis of two-year integrated programs of general and specialized subjects in the form of full-time education on the basis of IX grade graduates in primary, vocational and vocational schools.

At the meeting, the senators discussed the new version of the law on higher education of many of our compatriots, recognition of diplomas obtained abroad, guarantee of temporary residence for students, distance education, family education, inclusive education. He emphasized that it will be important to introduce legal clarifications to issues that are difficult to find solutions to their questions, such as

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasining Qonuni, 23.09.2020 yildagi O'RQ-637-son <https://lex.uz/docs/-5013007>
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasining Qonuni, 29.08.1997 yildagi 464-I-son <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-16188?ONDATE=05.01.2018%2002>

